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ADOPTING ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION (ADR) IN RESOLVING AIR CARRIERS AND AIR PASSENGERS CONFLICT IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Lack of a viable, practical and efficient Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanism limits the dispute resolution options in air carrier and air passenger conflict. Against this background, the research employs an armed chair method and provided the rationale for suggesting Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in resolving air carrier and air passenger conflict. The demerits of the litigation option and the practice of ADR in Nigeria and the European Union (EU) jurisdiction on air carrier/air passengers dispute resolution were highlighted. The research finds that the Nigerian legal and institutional regime are weak and lacks effective dispute resolution and enforcement mechanism. The existing dispute resolution mechanism and air passengers' dispute resolution and complaint procedure are not clearly defined and made easily accessible by aggrieved air passengers under the applicable regime. The research recommends for formal adoption of ADR scheme, especially negotiation and mediation techniques, to provide for a mandatory, uniform, simple, fast and practical method and determining disputes/complaints outside the litigation option. The regulatory institutions should improve both air carrier and air

passengers' education/positive engagements with enhance regulatory supervision and finally create an independent Air Passengers' Protection and Dispute Resolution Committee (APPDRC) to protect and resolve air carrier and air passenger disputes. This will strengthen air passengers' rights protection and dispute resolution architecture in the Nigerian aviation industry.

Keywords: Air Carrier, Air passenger, Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR), Negotiation/Mediation.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Dispute or conflict is inevitable in life, and the contract of air carriage is no exception. Dispute is faceless and is neither good nor bad, what is good or bad is how disputes are resolved. Conflict arising out of breach of air passengers' rights by air carriers are prevalent in Nigeria, and the existing legal framework on air carriers and air passengers' dispute resolution appears to be ineffective. Currently, there is a prevalent discontent by both consumers of goods and services in Nigeria,¹including air passengers. Air passengers whose rights are violated without adequate compensation, remedy, or enforcement by the relevant body may be left with litigation option. Unfortunately, employing the litigation option to resolve air passengers' dispute with airlines is detrimental and sometimes takes wasted years of litigation in the court of law. Delay in court proceeding can be tormenting to air passengers, even if judgment is awarded in their favour. For instance, the case of *British Airways v Atoyebi*² lingered for a decade after passing through 3 different courts. The case was filed in 2002 by the respondent and judgment delivered by the Supreme Court in 2014.

This paper examines Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in Nigeria and presented the rationale for suggesting Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in resolving air carriers and air passengers' disputes, highlighting the shortfalls of the litigation option. The paper then analysed some challenges of air passengers' complaint procedure and explored the practice of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in Nigeria and the European Union ADR practice in the aviation sector before making a case for the adoption of negotiation and mediation ADR mechanism in resolving air carrier and air passengers' dispute. The paper finally concludes and proffer some recommendations, including the establishment of Air Passengers' Protection and Dispute Resolution Committee (APPDRC) to easily resolve air carrier and air passengers' dispute.

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¹Ijewere Anthony, A. and Obaseki Stephen O., Consumerism in Nigeria, 188.

² [2014] LP ELR 23120 (SC). See also <http://fliphtml5.com/khqr/tmik/basic> Suit No: Sc.332/2010 (accessed 05 October, 2020).

2.1 SITUATING ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION (ADR) IN NIGERIA

For the purpose of this paper, the definition of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) by Bayo will be adopted. According to him, Alternative Dispute Resolution denotes all forms of dispute resolution other than litigation through the courts.³ ADR includes those decision-making processes besides litigation, including but not limited to negotiation, inquiry, mediation, conciliation, expert determination, arbitration etc.⁴ ADR is an encompassing theory of the different non-confrontational methods of conflict resolution, ranging from negotiation between two or more disputing parties through consensus building, mediation to arbitration.⁵ Thus, ADR is an alternative to litigation and not an entirely new concept or practice.

Historically, the introduction of numerous substitutes for dispute resolution aside litigation within the administration of justice system gained popularity in 1976. In that year, a conference on the causes of popular dissatisfaction with the judicial administration of justice was held and a 'multidoor courthouse' system was introduced to decongest the courts and improve the quality of justice to consumers.⁶ Consequently, ADR was formalized and is increasingly adopted in the resolution of disputes, ranging from simple disagreements to disputes that require expertise because of the nature of subject. The quest for better outcome and access to justice for members of the society (outside litigation) and de professionalizing the judicial process actually influenced the development of ADR processes.⁷ In all ADR processes, the proceedings are aimed at facilitating an outcome between the parties.

³Bayo Ojo, "Achieving Access to Justice through Alternative Dispute Resolution," *CI Arb.* vol. 1 no. 1, Kenya, (2013), 1.

⁴*Ibid.*

⁵Emah Savoir P., "ADR and the Oku Iboku-Ikot Offiong Conflict (1987-2005)" *Conflict Studies Quarterly* 19 (2017), 5.

⁶Menkel-Meadow, Carrie. "Mediation, arbitration, and alternative dispute resolution (ADR)." *International Encyclopedia of the Social and Behavioural Sciences*, No. 2015-59, (2015), 8.

⁷ *Ibid.*, 6. The involvement of local institutions and members of the society in the early 1960's and 70's and members of the neighbourhood with peculiar experiences in the resolution of dispute were major factors in advancing ADR. Similarly, breaking of lawyer's monopoly in the process of legal representation and engagement of community based institutions attributed to the development of ADR. See also Kruse, Katherine R., Bobbi McAdoo, and Sharon Press. "Client Problem Solving: Where ADR and Lawyering Skills Meet." *Elon L. Rev.* 7 (2015), 228-229.

The developments leading to the actual practice of ADR in Nigeria started with the inclusion of arbitration or conciliation in High Court Rules.⁸ The current legislation for ADR is the Arbitration and Mediation Act, 2023 (AMA, 2023).⁹ The AMA, 2023 repealed the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 2004 (ACA, 2004) which was enacted in 1988 following the UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration with little modifications.¹⁰ Thus, arbitration as a major form of ADR has over the years become the common means of settling commercial disputes domestically and internationally.¹¹ However, the AMA 2023 just like the repealed ACA, 2004 is focused on commercial arbitration with emphasis on arbitration and mediation scheme emphasizing the application and enforcement of the Convention on the Recognition of Foreign Arbitral Awards (the New York Convention) with little emphasis to other disputes such as contractual rights outside commercial transactions. Secondly, arbitration is often invoked where there is an existing clause in a commercial agreement to that effect. The paper attempts to make a case for the adoption of effective ADR mechanism in resolving air carrier and air passenger disputes. The rationale for suggesting ADR in resolving air passengers' dispute, particularly the adoption of negotiation and mediation is highlighted hereunder.

2.2 JUSTIFICATION FOR ADR IN RESOLVING AIR CARRIERS AND AIR PASSENGERS' DISPUTES

Litigation which is the common means of domestic dispute resolution in Nigeria is adversarial in nature.¹² As in most common law jurisdictions which practice the English

⁸Ayinla Lukman Alabi, "Implementation of Alternative Dispute Resolution in Nigeria: Possibilities and Hindrances." (PhD Dissertation, International Islamic University Malaysia, 2011), 12. See also section 18 of the High Court Act of the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, 2009.

⁹Arbitration and Mediation Act, 2023. This Act repeals the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004.

¹⁰The UNCITRAL Model Law, United Nations Documents A/40/17, Annex I and A/6/17 Annex I, adopted by the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law on 21 June 1985, as amended by the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law 7 July, 2006. The UNCITRAL Model Law is the legal framework of the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law. It provides the legislative guide for adoption by states for modernizing their laws for use by parties to commercial agreements.

¹¹Ayinla, L. A., A. K. Adebayo, and Bilikis A. A., "An appraisal of the nexus and disparities between arbitration and Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR)." *Nnamdi Azikiwe University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence* 8, no. 1 (2017), 184.

¹²Mathias Dawodu, OlaoyeOlalere and Debo Ogunmuyiwa, *Litigation and Dispute Resolution in Nigeria*. Second edition Global legal group. Available at <http://www.globallegalinsights.com> accessed 22 May 2022.

common law, Nigeria operates a court system with the judge playing the adversarial role.¹³ Under this system, court judgments are in the form of win-lose nature; clearly declaring winners and losers. The adversarial proceedings of courts will definitely affect the contractual relationship of air passengers and air carriers.¹⁴ It is said that no two people will go to court and become friends again. Air passengers and air carriers are parties to a contract of air carriage who will naturally disagree. How such disagreement is settled is important in defining the cordiality of future engagements. It is submitted that the negotiation and mediation mechanism will operate for the mutual benefit of both air passengers and air carriers and will assist in remodelling the existing dispute resolution scheme in the aviation sector. Adoption of ADR will also strengthen the relationship between air carriers and air passengers. Moreover, it is not economically wise for airlines to allow passengers to take them to court since customer satisfaction¹⁵ promotes customer allegiance, which ultimately means more profit for airlines.

It is the position of this paper that the demerits of litigation can be avoided by adopting a functional alternative dispute resolution scheme outside going to court. The following are some clear advantages of ADR¹⁶ in favour of air passengers' dispute resolution:

1. Technicalities of litigation will be avoided.
2. The Cost of litigation and services for legal practitioners will be minimized or eliminated.
3. Balancing the interest of air passengers and air carriers.
4. Speedy resolution of dispute between air carriers and passengers.
5. Airlines can employ a customer friendly approach during ADR with air passengers.¹⁷

¹³Ibid.

¹⁴Bollweg, Hans-Georg. "Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) in the Aviation Sector in Germany." *ZLW62* (2013), 401. ADR originates in USA in the 1960's following the access to justice movement when alternative modes of resolving disputes were intended and practiced in favour of less privileged members of the population to seek redress. See Creutzfeldt, Naomi J., and Christof Berlin. "ADR in aviation: European and national perspectives." *Civil Justice Quarterly*, 35 (2), (2016), 4.

¹⁵Baker, D. "Low-cost airlines management model and customer satisfaction." *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management* (2014), 8.

¹⁶ Rahman F., Advantages and disadvantages of ADR. Available at <https://www.scribd.com/document/481647392/Advantages-and-Disadvantages-of-ADR>, accessed on 25/09/2023.

¹⁷Ibid.

Other reasons why ADR is important in resolving disputes is that customer loyalty can be maintained by the airlines if disputes are resolved via ADR. The operation of ADR for air passengers' disputes will also complement and supplement the role of the courts in resolving air passengers' disputes. Effective ADR scheme in the aviation sector will expedite cooperation and synergy between institutions, air passengers and airlines in for a better and easy dispute resolution.

The Civil Aviation Act, 2022 mandates the Nigerian Civil Aviation Authority (NCAA) to come up, in consultation with air carriers and other stakeholders, with arrangements for compensation of aggrieved passengers.¹⁸ The spirit of the provision is a call for collaboration for the resolution of air carrier/passengers' dispute. Certainly, collaboration is a form of cooperation, understanding for easy and amicable dispute settlement. No doubt, the participation of airlines in the dispute resolution process will assist in making airlines respect the outcome. To what extent is this provision practically implemented is vital in assessing the effectiveness or otherwise of dispute resolution between air passengers and airlines. Below are some limitations in the manner disputes between air passengers and air carriers are resolved.

3.0 ANALYSIS OF SOME LIMITATIONS OF AIR PASSENGERS' COMPLAINT PROCEDURE

In the Nigerian aviation sector, disputes between air carriers and air passengers are to be resolved via a complaint procedure. An aggrieved air passenger is expected to lay a complaint if his or her right is breached by the air carrier. The term complaint has been defined by the Nigerian Civil Aviation Regulations, 2023 as an allegation made by an air passenger, a group of passengers or their legal heirs or representatives¹⁹ which must be made in writing.²⁰ The basic steps of the complaint procedure are that a passenger should first fill and submit a complaint form, which is available online. As a condition, the passenger must have notified the air carrier of such a breach and the complaint remains

¹⁸Civil Aviation Act, 2022 section 102 (1) and (2).

¹⁹Nigerian Civil Aviation Regulations 2023, (Nig. CARs 2023) Part 19, section 19.1.2.1 and section 19.24.14 states that complaints by air passengers to NCAA shall be in writing or by electronic means. Attachments of necessary supporting documents such as air ticket is also made part of the requirement of a formal complaint.

²⁰Nigerian Civil Aviation Regulations 2023, section 19.24.1.4. Initial complaint by air passengers to airlines must also be in writing. Some airlines in Nigeria ignore or pay less attention to passengers' complaints or even deliberately stay out of sight when a flight is delayed or cancelled.

unresolved before resorting to lodging a formal complaint to the Authority.²¹ Although under the Civil Aviation Regulations of 2015, passenger complaints are to be made to the Consumer Protection Directorate (CPD), the 2023 Regulation is silent on the existence and role of the CPD.²² After determining a complaint, findings of the CPD are communicated to the complainant. In some instances, meetings between the complainant, air carriers and the CPD are held to jointly resolve difficult complaints. The regulation is however, apparent that irrespective of the findings or involvement of the CPD in a complaint parties are free to seek further redress by legal or other appropriate means.

Similarly, the Nig. CARs 2023 mandates airlines to designate an officer for resolving air passengers' complaints, in practice most airlines are in violation of the provision. The section states:

“Every airline shall have a designated officer for the purpose of receiving and resolving complaints from its passengers. Such designated officers may liaise with the Authority where necessary. Every airline shall submit to the Authority its consumer complaint procedure manual, which shall be in accordance with its business module.”²³

This provision only states that airlines shall designate an officer for resolving complaints. Airlines may flout this provision if not properly supervised by the regulatory bodies. A cursory look at the provision gives airlines the discretion of liaising with NCAA in resolving complaints by employing the word 'may' in the provision above. This gives airlines the discretion to liaise with the Authority. In reality, airlines ignore passengers' complaints and can sometimes evade passengers with complaints or deliberately make complaint procedure complex and time-consuming. Similarly, air carriers may not be at sight for a passenger to place a complaint, especially if they are at fault and are aware that passengers are aggrieved.

²¹Authority denotes the Nigerian Civil Aviation Authority (NCAA) established by section 4 of the Civil Aviation Act, 2022. The Authority is headed by a Director General (DG).

²² Civil Aviation Regulations 2015, section 19.22.3. Alternatively, an air passenger may write a letter of complaint to the DG Nigerian Civil Aviation Authority (NCAA).

²³Nigerian Civil Aviation Regulations 2023, section 19.24.1.1.

The 2023 Regulations also provides that the NCAA is mandated to organise an administrative hearing to resolve air passengers' dispute through mediation.²⁴ However, the Regulations are silent on the composition of the administrative hearing. Unfortunately, this lacuna will render the provision impotent and ineffective in resolving air carrier and air passengers' dispute.

Language barrier could also be a challenge for non-English-speaking passengers, and writing a formal complaint by illiterate passengers is an impossibility. The absence of a provision on oral complaints and the method of taking complaints from illiterate passengers is a challenge of the complaint handling process. It is submitted that proper education of air passengers not only in English but the major languages in Nigeria (Hausa, Yoruba, and Igbo) will assist in effective complaints handling. With this in place, an average passenger will know his or her rights and choose an easy and efficient mode of dispute resolution, aside litigation. If a complaint procedure is characterised with difficulties, it will dissuade air passengers from laying complaints. It is recommended that all major airlines should have an office in the airport for handling air passengers' complaints under the supervision of the NCAA and passengers be allowed to lodge oral complaint in major languages (English, Hausa, Igbo, and Yoruba). Furthermore, it is argued that until the complaint procedure is expressly and practically made easy, air passengers will be discouraged to even lay complaints. The paper therefore recommends that air passengers' complaints procedure to be simple and less formal. The use of oral or telephone mode for receiving complaints will certainly simplify the process. The current practice of using a standard complaints form should not be made compulsory by airlines and the regulators, and the physical presence of an air passenger may be dispensed with. These measures, in addition to expeditious determination of complaints and award of necessary compensation to air passengers in, will enhance the efficiency of the dispute resolution scheme.

Airlines should be mandated to liaise with regulators, especially where passengers are aggrieved and are unwilling to cooperate with airlines. Staff of NCAA should be at sight to

²⁴Nigerian Civil Aviation Regulations 2023, section 19.27.1.1, dealing with Administrative Hearing Procedure.

enforce an established complaints-handling procedures with standard feedback procedure and replies to passengers' complaints. It is submitted that if airlines will attain to passengers' complaints and compensate them promptly, very few cases of complaints will be recorded and this will serve as one of the easiest methods of avoiding dispute. Although the Civil Aviation Act, 2022 mandates the Federal High Court, which has jurisdiction on aviation matters to adopt all legitimate measures to avoid unnecessary delays in proceedings,²⁵ it is unlikely that many cases will even be instituted by air passengers who may prefer a less technical and less formal dispute resolution mechanism to ventilate their grievances instead of approaching the court.

From the highlight of the challenges of air passengers' complaint procedure and the role of ADR mechanism in assisting and resolving air passengers' disputes, the paper proposes for the establishment of an independent, neutral and competent body for the determination of air passengers' rights complaints. A survey of the European Union Jurisdiction reveals how disputes between air carriers and air passengers are resolved through the ADR mechanism.

4. PRACTICE OF ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION (ADR) IN THE EUROPEAN UNION (EU) AND THE UNITED KINGDOM AVIATION SECTOR

Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) for all consumers in the European Union (EU) is generally regulated by the European Union directive for the establishment of ADR in sales and service contracts.²⁶ The directive is a uniform legal framework for consumer ADR, setting the standard for a robust ADR landscape in the EU jurisdiction.²⁷ The aim of the directive is to encourage consumers to voluntarily submit to an alternative means of dispute settlement procedure. The foundation of aviation ADR is firmly established by reference to the aim of the directive viz:

The purpose of this Directive is, through the achievement of a high level of consumer protection, to contribute to the proper functioning of the internal

²⁵Civil Aviation Act, 2022, section 87.

²⁶ European Union Council Directive on Alternative Dispute Resolution for Consumer Disputes, 2013/11. The Directive amends EC Regulation No. 2006/2004.

²⁷Creutzfeldt, Naomi J., and Christ of Berlin. "ADR in aviation: European and national perspectives." *Civil Justice Quarterly*, 1, (2016), 5.

market by ensuring that consumers can, on a voluntary basis, submit complaints against traders to entities offering independent, impartial, transparent, effective, fast and fair alternative dispute resolution procedures. This Directive is without prejudice to national legislation making participation in such procedures mandatory, provided that such legislation does not prevent the parties from exercising their right of access to the judicial system.²⁸

From the above provision, the main thrust of the directive is consumer protection. The directive tends to simplify submission of complaints by consumers against traders to an independent and impartial ADR process. It is also clear from the above provision that the directive is intended to facilitate out of court dispute resolution under the watch of an impartial entity. The level of independence, impartiality in disposing consumer complaints by such entities is what will determine the overall success of such bodies.

The directive also tends to simplify the submission of complaints by consumers against traders to independent and impartial ADR entities of member states.²⁹ The directive is a strict alternative to litigation without limiting parties to resort to litigation. Interestingly, however, the directive also contains provisions that will checkmate the impartiality of ADR entities. For instance, it provides that where ADR is funded exclusively by a trader, such ADR practitioner is not competent to preside or decide for parties.³⁰ The spirit of this provision is to dispel potential conflict of interest in the ADR entity.

Because of the nature of the EU, the directive will potentially encourage the development of different rules in member states, which may affect the procedure and operation of ADR practice in cross border disputes. However, one important characteristic of the ADR entities is independent governance and funding in accordance with the EU directive.³¹ It is provided that air passengers can also be charged a refundable nominal fee for ADR. It is

²⁸ European Union Council Directive on Alternative Dispute Resolution for Consumer Disputes, 2013/11, article 1.

²⁹ European Union Council Directive on Alternative Dispute Resolution for Consumer Disputes, 2013/11, article 4. An ADR entity is defined as an established durable body which offers alternative dispute resolution in accordance with the EU Directive.

³⁰ European Union Council Directive on Alternative Dispute Resolution for Consumer Disputes, 2013/11, article 2.

³¹ Consumer Complaints Handling and ADR: CAA Policy statement and notice of approval criteria for applicant ADR bodies. <https://publicapps.caa.co.uk/cap1286..>, accessed 15 December, 2022.

argued that funding ADR scheme independently will generally enhance the impartiality of dispute resolution. A closer look at the directive reveals that member states are at liberty to introduce rules on consumer protection and dispute resolution.³² It provides the basis for the operation of ADR by setting the minimum standard and guidelines for member states. The directive is therefore the basic foundation for the general operation of ADR in the EU.

Pursuant to the EU directive, the UK came up with air passengers' ADR policy, entitled the Civil Aviation Authority Policy on Consumer Complaints Handling and Alternative Dispute Resolution, 2023.³³ The main thrust of the policy is to comply with the EU directive on consumer ADR and provide an independent ADR entity for a fast out of court resolution of disputes.³⁴ The UK's ADR for the aviation industry was announced to assist air passengers and airlines resolve their disputes similarly practiced in other sectors such as the financial services and telecoms.³⁵

The UK's Civil Aviation Authority (CAA)³⁶ has advocated for the implementation of air passengers' ADR which cover areas where the CAA have authority to regulate and areas where it has oversight duties.³⁷ It is on record that the UK CAA received 20,000 cases in 2016 from air passengers who had reached a deadlock with airlines for refusing to pay compensation.³⁸ Currently, major airlines like the British Airways, Ryanair and EasyJet are covered by the ADR scheme, representing more than 70 percent of air travels from and

³² European Union Council Directive on Alternative Dispute Resolution for Consumer Disputes, 2013/11, article 2 (3).

³³Consumer Complaints Handling and ADR: CAA Policy statement and notice of approval criteria for applicant ADR bodies. <https://publicapps.caa.co.uk/cap1286..> accessed 15 December, 2022. *The UK CAA provides that in spite the result of the 2016 referendum and the controversy on the UK's membership of the EU, the European Union Council Directive on Alternative Dispute Resolution for Consumer Disputes, 2013/11 will continue to be relevant and applicable in relation to UK ADR practice in the future. The UK ADR policy is reviewed and updated with the latest issued in 2016.*

³⁴ European Union Council Directive on Alternative Dispute Resolution for Consumer Disputes, 2013/11, article 8. The article set a timeline of 90 days for determination of complaints to avoid delays in the determination of complaints.

³⁵ United Kingdom Civil Aviation Authority, How CAA protects consumers and promote the rights of UK air passengers, <http://publicapps.caa.co.uk/modalapplication.aspx?appid=11&mode=detail&id=7767> (accessed 15 December, 2022).

³⁶The UK Civil Aviation Authority is established by section 2 (1) of the UK Civil Aviation Act, 1982.

³⁷ The UK Civil Aviation Authority is the competent authority for ADR entities in the UK. All ADR entities must therefore seek approval from the CAA and shall operate in line with the standards set out by the Authority.

³⁸ Airlines receive 400 complaints a week - How a new Ombudsman could help. <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/finance/personalfinance/money-saving-tips/11743659/Airlines-receive-400-complaints-a-week-how-a-new-ombudsman-could-help.html> accessed 10 November, 2022.

to the UK. Interestingly, airlines are now bound to pay compensation after a fast and legally binding ADR process.³⁹

The UK has taken air passengers' ADR seriously and is employing CAA's legal powers and the consumer protection cooperation network to ensure that all airlines operating within the UK and other EU member states comply with the ADR scheme. For instance, in 2016 when CAA discovered two EU airlines (Croatia airlines and Wow air) were not complying with air passengers' rights to information on ADR, they were referred to their home authorities to take further action.⁴⁰ It is the view of the CAA that the future of effective complaints handling lie with the significant role of ADR schemes such as the consumer ombudsmen. This shows the level of optimism of the CAA in advocating for the full implementation of ADR in air passengers' dispute resolution.

It is important to mention that an ADR entity shall be independent, impartial and the members should possess requisite knowledge and skill.⁴¹ The ADR body is also accountable to presenting an annual report on their activities. The report must include statistics of cases received, solved, cases discontinued, the common conflict resolved, the causes of such conflict and recommendations. This role is similar to one of the major functions of an ombudsman; settling disputes and recommending ways of avoiding recurrence. It is submitted that such a report will trigger legal and policy reform. However, ADR practice in the UK aviation industry is not mandatory for all airlines, and therefore some airlines may continue to violate air passengers' rights. The research submits that participation in ADR should be made compulsory for all airlines to achieve uniformity and better dispute resolution for air passengers' dispute.

It is also submitted that the success of ADR is beneficial to the airlines, who naturally would want to keep the relationship with passengers for future patronage. Thus, a successful ADR mechanism serves the mutual benefit of both the airlines and air passengers. The

³⁹ How CAA protects and promotes legal rights of UK air passengers. <https://www.google.com/search?q=How+the+CAA+protects+consumers+and+promotes+the+legal+rights+of+UK+air+passenger&ie=utf-8&oe=utf-8&client=firefox-b-ab> accessed 16 December, 2022.

⁴⁰ United Kingdom Civil Aviation Authority, How CAA protects consumers and promote the rights of UK air passengers, <http://publicapps.caa.co.uk/modalapplication.aspx?appid=11&mode=detail&id=7767> (accessed 15 December, 2017). The UK ADR engaged and encouraged both airlines and air passengers in voluntary participating in ADR via campaign and awareness.

⁴¹ European Union Council Directive on Alternative Dispute Resolution for Consumer Disputes, 2013/11, article 6.

research finds that ADR in the aviation sector within the EU varies from one-member state to another and is yet to reach its full potential. As in other consumer sectors, the setup of ADR depends on the national context of each country.⁴² In the UK, for instance, it is the desire of the CAA to encourage the development of ADR practice on a voluntary basis and fully take full charge of all ADR bodies. Certainly, Nigeria can learn from the EU practice of ADR in their aviation industry to effectively promote the rights of air passengers and checkmate the excesses of air carriers. The paper particularly recommends for the adoption of Negotiation and mediation as tools for air carrier and air passenger dispute resolution in Nigeria.

5.0 ADOPTING NEGOTIATION AND MEDIATION IN RESOLVING AIR CARRIER/AIR PASSENGERS' DISPUTES IN NIGERIA

Negotiation is the process of resolving dispute through direct bargaining between the parties.⁴³ Negotiation is often used at the initial stage of dispute settlement, being practiced even between states. The Simplicity of the process is an advantage because parties acknowledge the claims of each other.⁴⁴ One of the main characteristics of negotiation is the absence of interference by a third party. It is submitted that there is mutual benefit in negotiation and air passengers' disputes can better be resolved by negotiation at an early stage because parties will be willing to give and take. Airlines can also benefit from negotiation because it is likely that air passengers will be willing to discuss with them and may even be willing to settle for less. In fact, both parties can save the cost of litigating by adopting mutual negotiation.

Alternatively, parties to a dispute may be assisted by a neutral third party who will facilitate resolution of the dispute through mediation. Mediation is a process in which a third party (usually neutral and unbiased) facilitates a negotiated consensual agreement between parties, without rendering a formal decision.⁴⁵ The advantage of mediation is that a

⁴²Alternative Dispute Resolution in the Air Passenger Rights Sector, Updated ECC Net Joint Project, September, 2019. available at https://www.europe-consummateurs.eu/fileadmin/Media/PDF/publications/etudes_et_rapports/Etudes_EN/Alternative_Dispute_Resoluti on_in_the_Air_Passenger_Rights_sector.pdf. accessed 16 January, 2023.

⁴³Emah Savoir P., "ADR and the Oku Iboku-Ikot Offiong Conflict (1987-2005), *Conflict Studies Quarterly*, 19, (2017), 5.

⁴⁴ Abdul Ghafur Hamid @ King Maung Sein., *Public International Law A Practical Approach*, 2nd Edition. (Prentice Hall Pearson Malaysia Sdn. Bhd., 2006), 405.

⁴⁵Menkel-Meadow, Carrie., 2.

mediator is a neutral third party who assists the parties in reaching a settlement. Unlike in litigation where the judge is to interpret and decide based on the law, a mediator is equitable to all parties and adopts a less technical procedure with no need for legal representation.

The Nig. CARs, 2023 provides that in the determination of complaint, the NCAA may advise air passengers and airlines to adopt mediation in resolving their dispute.⁴⁶ The provision is however silent on the selection and qualification of the mediator who will oversee the mediation process. It could be inferred that officers of the NCAA could be the mediators. However, air passengers may not be comfortable with NCAA officers as mediators because of the likelihood of bias from them. It is submitted that a mediator is a neutral third party and if there is doubt by a disputing party regarding the neutrality of a mediator, the process will not be successful. This argument is made because air passengers are already losing confidence in the NCAA staff, especially where some complaints of violations of their rights are not enforced by the NCAA staff. It is recommended that the mediators in aviation be neutral, whose qualification and impartiality be considered.

Mediation is a viable option for air passengers' dispute resolution because generally, some consumers consider that they lack the capacity and experience to fully pursue their rights⁴⁷ and may require guidance from a trusted mediator who will focus on the solution and who will give each party an opportunity to express their grievances. Some air passengers fall into this category because they see everything relating to the aviation industry as too complex to deal with. The paper therefore recommends for the adoption of negotiation and applauds the adoption of mediation by the regulations. However, there is a need for competent and independent mediators in the resolution of air passengers' dispute. Mediation can be an immediate follow-up if negotiation fails. Basically, mediation is an

⁴⁶Nigerian Civil Aviation Regulations 2023, section 19.26.1.1 (a) (i).

⁴⁷Santos, Cristiana. "Enhancing the Decision Making Process through Relevant Legal Information in Consumer Law Disputes—a Case Study in Air Transport Passenger Rights." In *SW4LAW+ DC@ JURIX*. 2014, 5.

assisted negotiation with all its traits.⁴⁸ The only difference between negotiation and mediation is just overseeing the resolution process by a mediator.

The paper therefore recommends that the Air Passengers' Protection and Dispute Resolution Committee (APPDRC) be established to serve as the mediation team to resolve air passengers' disputes. Proper coordination and synergy between the NCAA, APPDRC and the airlines is also recommended to achieve easy air passengers' dispute resolution that will restore the confidence of air passengers in the dispute resolution regime in Nigeria.

6.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

An effective dispute resolution procedure is an important element in a justice delivery system. It is not in doubt that air passengers continue to have dispute with airlines despite the existence of a legal and institutional framework for air passengers' protection and the judicial system is no best option for settling such dispute. The existing air passengers' dispute resolution mechanism in Nigeria is not completely effective. Some limitations of the existing mechanism of conflict resolution between air passengers and air carriers are; language barrier for non-English-speaking passengers (who are expected to write a formal complaint in English), formality of the complaint procedure which is inflexible and cumbersome, absence of a provision on oral complaints and the method of taking complaints from illiterate passengers, giving airlines the discretion of liaising with NCAA in resolving complaints could be abused thereby making the complaint procedure/dispute resolution difficult and time-consuming.

The paper posits that, from all the ADR options, negotiation, and mediation are the preferred options for the resolution of air passengers' rights dispute. To achieve an effective application of the negotiation and mediation options, simplicity and flexibility of the complaint procedure, educating air passengers in English, Hausa, Yoruba, and Igbo on their rights and the option to choose the mode of lodging complaints, including oral

⁴⁸Nair, Mr Pramod, and Mr Kumar Abhijeet. "Negotiation is the Basis for all ADR Methods: Critical Analysis." National Law School of India, (2013), 5.

complaint is recommended. Until a complaint procedure is practically made easy, air passengers will continue to be discouraged to even lay complaints.

Similarly, the physical presence of air passengers should be dispensed with and be given the option to negotiate with airlines via phone or by other mutual means of communication, complaints should also be expeditiously resolved to enhance the efficiency of the dispute resolution scheme. Airlines operating in Nigeria should also be educated on the rights of air passengers by the NCAA, the merits associated with ADR, the need to comply with air passengers' rights, liaise with regulators, especially where passengers are aggrieved and are unwilling to cooperate with airlines, close monitoring, supervision and enforcement of the regulations by the NCAA against defaulting airlines to avoid disputes.

In line with the finding that air passengers' rights in the EU jurisdiction is advanced with a better protection scheme for air passengers. Nigeria can learn a lot from that jurisdiction, especially on the role of strong institutional framework in protecting air passengers' rights, positive engagements with airlines in favour of air passengers, enforcement mechanism such as issuing penalties and sanctions to airlines and the role of air passengers' and consumer protection institutions and bodies in the application of effective alternative dispute resolution to easily and effectively resolve air passengers' dispute.

The paper finally recommends for the establishment of an independent, neutral and competent body for the determination of air passengers' rights complaints to be named "Air Passengers' Protection and Dispute Resolution Committee (APPDRC)". Proper coordination and synergy between the airlines, NCAA and APPDRC and airlines will facilitate dispute resolution that will restore the confidence of air passengers in the aviation dispute resolution regime in Nigeria.